

Post-contrast multi-parametric mapping from only pre-contrast conventional weighted images

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Motivation: Gadolinium-based contrast agents (GBCAs) have become a cornerstone in clinical routine for lesions characterization and treatment monitoring. However, issues such as safety concerns related to deposition of GBCA in the body and brain, prolonged acquisitions, and cost increase advocate against its usage.

Goal: To replace the usage of GBCAs in post-contrast imaging with parametric maps and deep learning.

Approach: A cascade of two convolutional-neural-networks for pre- and post-contrast parametric mapping and the synthesis of post-contrast T1-weighted images from only two pre-contrast conventional weighted images.

Results: The proposed approach presents potential for predicting post-contrast T1w-enhancement without the usage of GBCAs.

Impact: The proposed deep learning approach provides both pre- and post-contrast parametric maps and, consequently, the capability of synthesizing any post-contrast image from only two pre-contrast conventional weighted images. Thus, it paves the way towards GBCAs-free acquisitions.

Purpose: Gadolinium-based contrast agents (GBCAs) are a cornerstone for detection, characterization and monitoring of brain tumors due to their ability to reveal blood-brain-barrier (BBB) breakdown¹. Although GBCAs are considered safe, up to 2.4% of patients suffer from mild adverse reactions² and, also, their possible deposition in tissues has recently raised safety concerns³. In addition, the usage of GBCAs results in patient discomfort, additional cost and prolonged scan time. Thus, making GBCAs unnecessary would be highly advantageous. With this goal in mind, parametric maps could play a crucial role due to their known ability to detect subtle tumor changes^{4,5}.

In this work, we propose a deep learning approach for pre- and post-contrast parametric mapping and the synthesis of post-contrast T1-weighted (post-T1w) images. Only two pre-contrast conventional weighted images—a T1-weighted (T1w) and a T2-weighted (T2w)—are used as input.

Methods:

Dataset and preprocessing:

14 patients with different grades of gliomas who had undergone tumor resection were scanned, after IRB approval and written informed consent, in a 3T GE Healthcare scanner. T1w, T2w, T2w-FLAIR, and post-T1w were acquired together with MAGiC⁶, a fast multi-parametric mapping technique. Images were co-registered and skull-stripped. Next, weighted images were analyzed by HD-GLIO⁷ to segment: (a) T1w-enhancement (T1e), and (b) T2w/T2w-FLAIR hyperintensity (T2h). Finally, each weighted image was normalized by its average intensity prior to the convolutional-neural-network (CNN).

Proposed approach:

We propose a cascade of two CNNs, namely, an extraction CNN and a prediction CNN (see Figure 1). The first CNN extracts the quantitative T1, T2, and PD maps whose information is embedded in the T1w and T2w. The second CNN takes these T1 and T2 maps and predicts the corresponding post-contrast (i.e., after GBCA administration) T1 and T2 maps. This prediction of the GBCA-related information is performed using both the tissue information derived from the pre-contrast maps and the extra knowledge extracted from the post-T1w and T2w during the self-supervised training. Training with T2w images, which are virtually invariant to contrast administration⁵, ensures that the post-contrast maps are numerically and physically coherent. Both CNNs share the architecture of Moya-Sáez et al.⁸ except for the number of inputs.

Training is 2-fold; step 1) the extraction CNN is trained via supervised learning with MAGiC maps as reference. The loss function is the l1-norm. Step 2) Keeping the weights of the extraction CNN fixed, the prediction network is trained with a self-supervised learning procedure similar to that proposed in Moya-Sáez et al.⁹. Post-T1w and T2w are used as references and the loss function is:

$$L_{\text{step2}} = \|(\text{postT1w}_{\text{syn}} - \text{postT1w}_{\text{acq}})\|_{\ell_1} + \|(\text{T2w}_{\text{syn}} - \text{T2w}_{\text{acq}})\|_{\ell_1} + \lambda \| M \odot (\Delta \text{T1w}_{\text{syn}} - \Delta \text{T1w}_{\text{acq}})\|_{\ell_1}$$

where $\text{postT1w}_{\text{syn}}$ and $\text{postT1w}_{\text{acq}}$ are the synthesized and acquired post-T1w, respectively. A similar distinction is applied to the T2w. M is a binary mask with positive values in the T1e regions, $\Delta \text{T1w}_{\text{syn}}$ and $\Delta \text{T1w}_{\text{acq}}$ are the GBCA intakes (i.e., $\text{postT1w}_{\text{syn}} - \text{T1w}_{\text{acq}}$ and $\text{postT1w}_{\text{acq}} - \text{postT1w}_{\text{acq}}$, respectively). We stress that the post-T1w and the mask are only needed for training.

Cross-validation was carried out *via* leave-one-out. For each data splitting, one patient is used for testing and the remaining patients are randomly split between training (11 patients) and early-stopping validation (2 patients). Transfer learning was

employed; in the extraction CNN by pre-training with a synthetic dataset⁸, and in the prediction CNN by pre-training with a large public dataset¹⁰. Both CNNs were trained with Adam ($\text{lr}=1\text{e-}4$), $\text{batchsize}=4$, and $\lambda=100$.

Results:

Figure 2 displays the pre-contrast MAGiC and synthetic parametric maps and also the percentage error between both. Figure 3 shows the pre- and post-contrast synthetic parametric maps, whereas Figure 4 shows the synthesized and acquired post-T1w images. The ground-truth and synthetic segmentations are also shown.

Discussion:

These preliminary results show how using only pre-contrast weighted images (i.e., acquired without GBCAs) is feasible not only to extract pre-contrast parametric maps but also to predict post-contrast maps. These maps may add value towards automatic enhancement quantification^{4,5}. MAGiC and synthetic pre-contrast maps present similar values (see Figure 2). Additionally, the predicted post-contrast maps have the capability of synthesizing post-contrast weighted images with visual resemblance to the acquired counterparts as shown in Figure 4. Despite the differences visible in Figure 4 between the ground-truth and the synthetic T1w-enhancement segmentations, the clinical value of both could potentially be the same. Future lines of research include the comparison of the synthetic post-contrast parametric maps with those obtained with other well-accepted techniques as well as validation of the approach with a larger cohort.

Conclusion:

We proposed a proof-of-concept for pre- and post-contrast multi-parametric mapping and the synthesis of post-T1w images, using only two pre-contrast conventional weighted images. Preliminary results suggest its potential for predicting post-contrast T1w-enhancement without GBCAs.

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Figure 3: A representative axial slice of the pre-contrast and post-contrast synthetic parametric maps computed with deep learning for various test patients. a) Pre-contrast T1 maps. b) Post-contrast T1 maps. c) Pre-contrast T2 maps. d) Post-contrast T2 maps. The pre- and post-contrast T1 and T2 values are measured in seconds [s]. Arrows highlight a shortening in the T1 values that can be noticed within the T1w-enhancement region, which is in agreement with the literature¹. This behavior also occurs in the T2 but to a much lower extent. Note that b) and d) correspond to the output of step 2.

Figure 4: A representative axial slice of the synthesized post-T1w images for different test patients. a) Acquired post-T1w. b) Synthetic post-T1w. c) Ground-truth segmentation mask of HD-GLIO. d) Segmentation mask of HD-GLIO using the synthetic post-T1w instead of the acquired one. Note that the synthetic post-T1w images are synthesized from the post-contrast parametric maps shown in Figure 3 using the theoretical equation that describes MR image intensity. Visual resemblance is noticeable between the synthesized and the acquired images. Yellow label: T1e, red label: T2h.